

Extended material to “Evaluation and Measurement of Software Process Improvement - A Systematic Literature Review”

Michael Unterkalmsteiner, Tony Gorschek, A.K.M. Moinul Islam,
Chow Kian Cheng, Rahadian Bayu Permadi, Robert Feldt

October 5, 2020

1 Overview

This document provides extended material to the publication “Evaluation and Measurement of Software Process Improvement - A Systematic Literature Review”. Section 2 describes how the initial search was conducted in order to identify existing systematic reviews regarding software process improvements. Section 3 lists in detail the identified SPI initiatives.

2 Preliminary search

In order to decide if the systematic review should be executed or not, a preliminary search on the topic was made. The search should identify systematic and traditional reviews targeting software process improvement.

The searches were conducted on Compendex, Inspec and Google on 2008/11/03.

2.1 Search based on synonyms for “systematic review”

The synonyms for "systematic review" used in the search string are listed in [1]. The search string was applied on the title, keywords and abstract fields as follows:

```
((SPI OR "Software process improvement") AND ("systematic review" OR "research review" OR "research synthesis" OR "research integration" OR "systematic overview" OR "systematic research synthesis" OR "integrative research review" OR "integrative review")) wn KY
```

Result: 3 publications (1 duplicate).

Due to the low response, an additional search with an equivalent search string was executed on Google. Clearly, the response was higher (1730 results), but it contained many duplicates and irrelevant results. In total, 5 systematic reviews were found [2–6], of which none addresses our research questions.

2.2 Broader search based on “review” or “literature review”

The second search was executed with the following search string:

```
((SPI OR "Software process improvement") AND (review OR "literature review")) wn KY
```

Result: 116 publications (20 duplicates).

By reading the title and the abstract of the 117 results:

- 31 were not in the field of Computer Science
- 66 were not discussing reviews or literature reviews at all

The remaining 19 publications [7–25], which were assessed by reading the full text, did not address our research questions and/or did not provide a systematic review of the SPI literature as it is intended by our review.

3 SPI initiatives

We categorized the studies according to the presented SPI initiative as follows:

- **Framework:** this group contains frameworks/models like CMM, international standards like ISO/IEC 15504 (SPICE) and business management strategies like Six Sigma. For the analysis, we further broke down this category into:
 - Established frameworks - CMM, CMMI, ISO/IEC 15504 (SPICE), Six-Sigma, PSP, TSP, QIP, TQM, IDEAL, PDCA. The references to this group can be found in the original publication by Unterkalmsteiner et al.
 - Combined frameworks - two or more established frameworks are used in combination to implement the SPI initiative (Table 1).
 - Derived frameworks - an established framework is extended or refined to fulfill the specific needs (Table 2).
 - Own framework - the study proposes a new framework without reference to one of the established frameworks (Table 3).
 - Limited framework - the framework targets only a specific process area (Table 4).
- **Practices:** software engineering practices which can be applied in one or more phases of the software development life-cycle (e.g. inspections, test-driven development, etc.). See Table 7 for practices, Table 5 where frameworks and practices are combined and Table 5 where practices and tools are combined.
- **Tools:** software applications that support software engineering practices (see Table 8 for tools and Table 6 where frameworks and tools are combined).

Table 1: Combined frameworks

SPI initiative	Study
BOOTSTRAP + GQM (PROFES)	[26–28]
CMMI + ISO 9001 + MPS.BR	[29, 30]
CMMI + Six Sigma	[31]
CMM + GQM	[32]
CMM + Six Sigma	[33]
CMM + RE maturity model	[34]
CMM + AMI (Assess, analyze, metricate, improve)	[35]
CMM + Raytheon’s three-phase process-improvement paradigm	[36]
CMM (SW-CMM) + Other (EVM and TSP)	[37]
SPICE + IEC 61508	[38]
SPICE + ISO 12207	[39]
QIP + ISO 12207	[40]
Six Sigma + GQM	[41]
TSP + GQM	[42]
PSP + Own Model [SW-CMM + Other (EVM and TSP)]	[43]
ISO + CMM + Other Frameworks	[44]
CMMI + TSP + PSP	[45]
ISO 9000 + CMM + CMMI + SPICE	[46]
QIP + CMM + ISO 9001	[47]

Table 2: Derived frameworks

SPI initiative	Study
TSPi (Derived from TSP)	[48]
RAPID (Assessment model based on SPICE)	[49]
Quality model for continuous improvement (Six Sigma -> CMMI -> EFQM)	[50]
Knowledge Based SPI (Derived from IDEAL)	[51]
TCS-QMS (SW-CMM + People-CMM + Six Sigma)	[52]
PQM (Platform for Quality Management - Derived from TQM) + AMM (Active Measurement Model)	[53]
Unnamed framework (Derived from CMM)	[54]

Table 3: Own framework

SPI initiative	Study
ASPE-MS (Approach for Software Process Establishment in Micro and Small Companies)	[55]
P-SPI (Product Focused SPI)	[56]
FMESP (Framework for the Modelling and Measurement of Software Processes)	[57]
ASAP (Avaya Software Assessment Process)	[58]
Unnamed framework	[59,60]

Table 4: Limited framework

SPI initiative	Study
REPEAT (Requirement Engineering)	[61]
MAUI (Measure, Alert, Understand and Improve)	[62]
MTPF (Minimal Test Practice Framework)	[63]
OMA (Observe-Mine-Adopt)	[64]
Software Testing Metrics Framework	[65]
GQM + Software process for a specific application domain	[66]
Multiview Framework (Derived from GQM)	[67]
Unnamed framework	[68]

Table 5: Framework & Practice

SPI initiative	Study
CMM + Software development and maintenance methodologies (SDMMs) + Structural and Cultural Change	[69]
CMM + Practice Quality Improvement	[70]
CMM + Practices (Peer review, unit test planning, Development integration testing)	[71]
CMM + Practice (measurement planning)	[72]
CMMI + Practice (Gasoline System Product line development approach - GS approach)	[73]
Six Sigma + XP	[74]
SPICE (ISO/IEC TR 15504) + Practice (Development System Security Process)	[75]

Table 6: Framework & Tool

SPI initiative	Study
PSP + TT (Tool)	[76]

Table 7: Practices

SPI initiative	Study
APPLY (Amplified Process Performance LaYout)	[15, 77]
Action Learning	[78]
Configuration Control and Error Analysis	[79]
Collocated inspections, intensive coaching, and feature-oriented development teams	[80]
REP (Requirement Engineering Process)	[81, 82]
Sw Product Management	[83]
ROD (Reuse Oriented Development)	[84]
Iterative Improvement Process within Agile	[85]
Reuse	[86]
XP	[87]
BiDfect (Defect management)	[88]
Code Review	[89]
Agile Software Process	[90]
Inspection - usage-based reading	[91]
Structured Software Development and Maintenance Methodology	[92]
Technology Transfer Macro-Process	[93]
Application and evaluation of four key requirement engineering techniques	[94]
Using group support system for inspection meeting	[95]
Inspection + Testing	[96, 97]
Use of evolution activity metrics by means of the application of a sequential statistical test	[98]
Improve project management (keeping track of effort and schedules), software inspections, use of a defined development process, source code metrics collection and analysis)	[99]
Introduction of practices and tools for configuration and change management	[100]
PRB (Perspective-based Reading) inspection	[101]
Component-level test automation & Test-driven development	[102]
Different inspection methods (Checklist based reading vs. Scenario based reading) are compared	[103]
Learning from Success	[104]

Table 8: Tools

SPI initiative	Study
SQUID (Software Quality In the Development Process)	[105]
Automated RE Management	[106]
Configuration Management System	[107]
Use Case Models	[108]
e-R&D	[109]
ReleasePlanner, which implements a practice called EVOLVE*	[110]
Test management automation	[111]
AMEDATO	[112]
Unnamed Tool	[113]

References

- [1] J. C. de Almeida Biolchini, P. G. Mian, A. C. C. Natali, T. U. Conte, and G. H. Travassos, “Scientific research ontology to support systematic review in software engineering,” *Advanced Engineering Informatics*, vol. 21, no. 2, pp. 133–151, Apr. 2007.
- [2] M. T. Baldassarre, N. Boffoli, D. Caivano, and G. Visaggio, “A Hands-On approach for teaching systematic review,” in *Proceedings of the 9th international conference on Product-Focused Software Process Improvement*, 2008, pp. 415–426.
- [3] F. O. Bjørnson and T. Dingsøy, “Knowledge management in software engineering: A systematic review of studied concepts, findings and research methods used,” *Information and Software Technology*, vol. 50, no. 11, pp. 1055–1068, Oct. 2008.
- [4] M. Staples and M. Niazi, “Systematic review of organizational motivations for adopting CMM-based SPI,” *Information and Software Technology*, vol. 50, no. 7-8, pp. 605–620, 2008.
- [5] O. Pedreira, M. Piattini, M. R. Luaces, and N. R. Brisaboa, “A systematic review of software process tailoring,” *SIGSOFT Softw. Eng. Notes*, vol. 32, no. 3, pp. 1–6, 2007.
- [6] F. J. Pino, F. García, and M. Piattini, “Software process improvement in small and medium software enterprises: a systematic review,” *Software Quality Control*, vol. 16, no. 2, pp. 237–261, 2008.
- [7] M. Montoni and A. Rocha, “A methodology for identifying critical success factors that influence software process improvement initiatives: An application in the brazilian software industry,” in *Software Process Improvement*, 2007, pp. 175–186.
- [8] M. Niazi, C. Hickman, R. Ahmad, and M. A. Babar, “A model for requirements change management: Implementation of CMMI level 2 specific practice,” in *Proceedings of the 9th international conference on Product-Focused Software Process Improvement*, 2008, pp. 143–157.
- [9] T. Dybå, “An instrument for measuring the key factors of success in software process improvement,” *Empirical Software Engineering*, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 357–90, 2000.
- [10] K. Cai, J. W. Cangussu, R. A. DeCarlo, and A. P. Mathur, “An overview of software cybernetics,” in *Proceedings of the Eleventh Annual International Workshop on Software Technology and Engineering Practice*, 2003, pp. 77–86.
- [11] L. Liao, H. K. N. Leung, and Y. Qu, “Automated support of quality improvement,” in *IASTED Conf. on Software Engineering and Applications*, 2004, pp. 696–702.

- [12] R. Y. S. de Oliveira, P. G. Ferreira, A. Alvaro, E. S. de Almeida, and S. R. de Lemos Meira, "Code inspection - a review," in *9th International Conference on Enterprise Information Systems*, 2007, pp. 537–540.
- [13] P. Barthelmeß, "Collaboration and coordination in process-centered software development environments: a review of the literature," *Information and Software Technology*, vol. 45, no. 13, pp. 911–928, Oct. 2003.
- [14] A. Farooq and R. R. Dumke, "Developing and applying a consolidated evaluation framework to analyze test process improvement approaches," in *Software Process and Product Measurement: International Conference, IWSM-Mensura 2007*. Springer-Verlag, 2008, pp. 114–128.
- [15] S. A. Ajila and D. Wu, "Empirical study of the effects of open source adoption on software development economics," *Journal of Systems and Software*, vol. 80, no. 9, pp. 1517–1529, 2007.
- [16] T. Dybå, "Factors of software process improvement success in small and large organizations: an empirical study in the scandinavian context," in *Proceedings of the 9th European software engineering conference held jointly with 11th ACM SIGSOFT international symposium on Foundations of software engineering*, 2003, pp. 148–157.
- [17] M. Kauppinen, M. Vartiainen, J. Kontio, S. Kujala, and R. Sulonen, "Implementing requirements engineering processes throughout organizations: success factors and challenges," *Information and Software Technology*, vol. 46, no. 14, pp. 937–953, Nov. 2004.
- [18] S. Balsamo, A. D. Marco, P. Inverardi, and M. Simeoni, "Model-Based performance prediction in software development: A survey," *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering*, vol. 30, no. 5, pp. 295–310, 2004.
- [19] B. Hansen, J. Rose, and G. Tjørnehøj, "Prescription, description, reflection: the shape of the software process improvement field," *International Journal of Information Management*, vol. 24, no. 6, pp. 457–472, Dec. 2004.
- [20] M. Niazi, "Software process improvement: A road to success," in *Product-Focused Software Process Improvement*, 2006, pp. 395–401.
- [21] M. S. Krishnan, T. Mukhopadhyay, and D. Zubrow, "Software process models and project performance," *Information Systems Frontiers*, vol. 1, no. 3, pp. 267–277, 1999.
- [22] M. A. Serrano, "State of the art and future of research in software process improvement," in *Proceedings of the 28th Annual International Computer Software and Applications Conference - Volume 01*, 2004, p. 239.
- [23] M. J. Gallivan, "Strategies for implementing new software processes: an evaluation of a contingency framework," in *Proceedings of the 1996 ACM SIGCPR/SIGMIS conference on Computer personnel research*. Denver, Colorado, United States: ACM, 1996, pp. 313–325.
- [24] W. Jiangping, Y. Jianmei, and H. Huiyuan, "Support structure of knowledge management in software process improvement," in *Proceedings of the IFIP 17th World Computer Congress - TC8 Stream on Information Systems: The e-Business Challenge*, 2002, pp. 17–29.
- [25] W. Scacchi, J. Feller, B. Fitzgerald, S. Hissam, and K. Lakhani, "Understanding Free/Open source software development processes," *Software Process: Improvement and Practice*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 95–105, 2006.
- [26] A. Birk, P. Derks, D. Hamann, J. Hirvensalo, M. Oivo, E. Rodenbach, R. van Solingen, and J. Taramaa, "Applications of measurement in product-focused process improvement: a comparative industrial case study," in *Proceedings 5th International Software Metrics Symposium (METRICS)*, Bethesda, 1998, pp. 105–8.
- [27] J. Jarvinen and R. van Solingen, "Establishing continuous assessment using measurements," in *Proceedings 1st International Conference on Product Focused Software Process Improvement (PROFES)*, Oulu, Finland, 1999, pp. 49–67.
- [28] J. Jarvinen, D. Hamann, and R. van Solingen, "On integrating assessment and measurement: towards continuous assessment of software engineering processes," in *Proceedings 6th International Software Metrics Symposium (METRICS)*, Boca Raton, 1999, pp. 22–30.
- [29] A. Ferreira, G. Santos, R. Cerqueira, M. Montoni, A. Barreto, A. S. Barreto, and A. Rocha, "Applying ISO 9001:2000, MPS.BR and CMMI to achieve software process maturity: BL Informatica's pathway," in *Proceedings 29th International Conference on Software Engineering (ICSE)*, Minneapolis, 2007, pp. 642–651.

- [30] A. I. F. Ferreira, G. Santos, R. Cerqueira, M. Montoni, A. Barreto, A. R. Rocha, A. O. S. Barreto, and R. C. Silva, "ROI of software process improvement at BL Informatica: SPIIndex is really worth it," *Software Process Improvement and Practice*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 311–318, Jul. 2008.
- [31] Z. Xiaosong, H. Zhen, ZhangMin, W. Jing, and Y. Dainuan, "Process integration of six sigma and CMMI," in *Proceedings 6th International Conference on Industrial Informatics (INDIN)*, Singapore, China, 2008, pp. 1650–1653.
- [32] R. van Solingen, "Measuring the ROI of software process improvement," *IEEE Softw.*, vol. 21, no. 3, pp. 32–38, May 2004.
- [33] M. Murugappan and G. Keeni, "Quality improvement-the six sigma way," in *Proceedings 1st Asia-Pacific Conference on Quality Software (APAQS)*, Hong Kong, China, 2000, pp. 248–57.
- [34] I. Sommerville and J. Ransom, "An empirical study of industrial requirements engineering process assessment and improvement," *ACM Transactions on Software Engineering and Methodology*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 85–117, Jan. 2005.
- [35] A. Kuntzmann-Combelles, "Quantitative approach to software process improvement," in *Objective Software Quality*, ser. Lecture Notes in Computer Science. Berlin, Germany: Springer, 1995, vol. 926, pp. 16–30.
- [36] R. Dion, "Process improvement and the corporate balance sheet," *IEEE Softw.*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 28–35, Jul. 1993.
- [37] L. Pracchia, "TheAV-8B team learns synergy of EVM and TSP accelerates software process improvement," *CrossTalk*, no. 1, pp. 20–22, 2004.
- [38] G. Spork and U. Pichler, "Establishment of a performance driven improvement programme," *Software Process Improvement and Practice*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 371–382, Jul. 2008.
- [39] B. Moreau, C. Lassudrie, B. Nicolas, O. l'Homme, C. d'Anterroches, and G. L. Gall, "Software quality improvement in France Telecom research center," *Software Process Improvement and Practice*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 135–44, Jul. 2003.
- [40] L. Scott, R. Jeffery, L. Carvalho, J. D'Ambra, and P. Rutherford, "Practical software process improvement - the IMPACT project," in *Proceedings 13th Australian Software Engineering Conference (ASWEC)*, Canberra, Australia, 2001, pp. 182–9.
- [41] M. K. Daskalantonakis, "A practical view of software measurement and implementation experiences within Motorola," *IEEE Trans. Softw. Eng.*, vol. 18, no. 11, pp. 998–1010, Nov. 1992.
- [42] B. R. V. Kinsky and M. Robey, "A case study: GQM and TSP in a software engineering capstone project," in *Proceedings 18th Software Engineering Education Conference (CSEET)*, Ottawa, Canada, 2005, pp. 215–222.
- [43] M. Russ and J. McGregor, "A software development process for small projects," *IEEE Softw.*, vol. 17, no. 5, pp. 96–101, Sep. 2000.
- [44] J. Kuilboer and N. Ashrafi, "Software process improvement deployment: an empirical perspective," *Journal of Information Technology Management*, vol. 10, no. 3-4, pp. 35–47, 1999.
- [45] P. Miller, "An SEI process improvement path to software quality," in *Proceedings 6th International Conference on the Quality of Information and Communication Technology (QUATIC)*, Lisbon, Portugal, 2007, pp. 12–18.
- [46] E. Savioja and M. Tukiainen, "Measurement practices in financial software industry," *Software Process Improvement and Practice*, vol. 12, no. 6, pp. 585–595, Nov. 2007.
- [47] F. McGarry and B. Decker, "Attaining level 5 in CMM process maturity," *IEEE Softw.*, vol. 19, no. 6, pp. 87–96, Nov. 2002.
- [48] G. Cuevas, J. C. Manzano, T. S. Feliu, J. Mejia, M. Munoz, and S. Bayona, "Impact of TSPi on software projects," in *4th Congress of Electronics, Robotics and Automotive Mechanics (CERMA)*, Cuernavaca, Mexico, 2007, pp. 706–711.
- [49] A. Cater-Steel, M. Toleman, and T. Rout, "Process improvement for small firms: An evaluation of the RAPID assessment-based method," *Information and Software Technology*, vol. 48, no. 5, pp. 323–334, May 2006.
- [50] S. Golubic, "Influence of software development process capability on product quality," in *Proceedings 8th International Conference on Telecommunications (ConTEL)*, Zagreb, Croatia, 2005, pp. 457–63.

- [51] K. Alagarsamy, S. Justus, and K. Iyakutti, "The knowledge based software process improvement program: A rational analysis," in *International Conference on Software Engineering Advances (ICSEA)*, Cap Esterel, France, 2007, p. 61.
- [52] M. Murugappan and G. Keeni, "Blending CMM and six sigma to meet business goals," *IEEE Softw.*, vol. 20, no. 2, pp. 42–8, Mar. 2003.
- [53] Q. Wang and M. Li, "Measuring and improving software process in China," in *Proceedings International Symposium on Empirical Software Engineering*, Noosa Heads, Australia, 2005, pp. 183–192.
- [54] S. Otoyá and N. Cerpa, "An experience: a small software company attempting to improve its process," in *Proceedings 9th International Workshop Software Technology and Engineering Practice (STEP)*, Pittsburgh, 1999, pp. 153–60.
- [55] C. von Wangenheim, S. Weber, J. Hauck, and G. Trentin, "Experiences on establishing software processes in small companies," *Information and Software Technology*, vol. 48, no. 9, pp. 890–900, Sep. 2006.
- [56] J. Trienekens, R. Kusters, and R. van Solingen, "Product focused software process improvement: concepts and experiences from industry," *Software Quality Journal*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 269–81, Dec. 2001.
- [57] G. Canfora, F. Garcia, M. Piattini, F. Ruiz, and C. Visaggio, "Applying a framework for the improvement of software process maturity," *Software - Practice and Experience*, vol. 36, no. 3, pp. 283–304, Mar. 2006.
- [58] D. Weiss, D. Bennett, J. Payseur, P. Tendick, and P. Zhang, "Goal-oriented software assessment," in *Proceedings 24th International Conference on Software Engineering (ICSE)*, Orlando, 2002, pp. 221–31.
- [59] J. Iversen and L. Mathiassen, "Cultivation and engineering of a software metrics program," *Information Systems Journal*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 3–19, Jan. 2003.
- [60] T. Tanaka, K. Sakamoto, S. Kusumoto, K. Matsumoto, and T. Kikuno, "Improvement of software process by process description and benefit estimation," in *Proceedings 17th International Conference on Software Engineering (ICSE)*, Seattle, 1995, pp. 123–32.
- [61] B. Regnell, P. Beremark, and O. Eklundh, "A market-driven requirements engineering process: results from an industrial process improvement programme," *Requirements Engineering*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 121–9, Jun. 1998.
- [62] L. Suardi, "How to manage your software product life cycle with MAUI," *Comm. ACM*, vol. 47, no. 3, pp. 89–94, Mar. 2004.
- [63] D. Karlström, P. Runeson, and S. Norden, "A minimal test practice framework for emerging software organizations," *Software Testing, Verification and Reliability*, vol. 15, no. 3, pp. 145–66, Sep. 2005.
- [64] J. H. Hayes, N. Mohamed, and T. H. Gao, "Observe-mine-adopt (OMA): an agile way to enhance software maintainability," *Journal of Software Maintenance and Evolution*, vol. 15, no. 5, pp. 297–323, Sep. 2003.
- [65] L. Lazic and N. Mastorakis, "Cost effective software test metrics," *WSEAS Transactions on Computers*, vol. 7, no. 6, pp. 599–619, Jun. 2008.
- [66] J. Zettell, F. Maurer, J. Münch, and L. Wong, "LIPE: a lightweight process for e-business startup companies based on extreme programming," in *Product Focused Software Process Improvement*, ser. Lecture Notes in Computer Science. Berlin, Germany: Springer, 2001, vol. 2188, pp. 255–70.
- [67] G. Visaggio, P. Ardimento, M. Baldassarre, and D. Caivano, "Assessing multiview framework (MF) comprehensibility and efficiency: A replicated experiment," *Information and Software Technology*, vol. 48, no. 5, pp. 313–22, May 2006.
- [68] B. List, R. Bruckner, and J. Kapaun, "Holistic software process performance measurement from the stakeholders' perspective," in *Proceedings 16th International Workshop on Database and Expert Systems Applications (DEXA)*, Copenhagen, Denmark, 2005, pp. 941–7.
- [69] K. Nelson, M. Buche, and H. Nelson, "Structural change and change advocacy: a study in becoming a software engineering organization," in *Proceedings 34th Annual Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (HICSS)*, Maui, 2001, p. 9 pp.
- [70] C. Hollenbach, R. Young, A. Pflugrad, and D. Smith, "Combining quality and software improvement," *Comm. ACM*, vol. 40, no. 6, pp. 41–5, Jun. 1997.

- [71] J. A. Lane and D. Zubrow, "Integrating measurement with improvement: An action-oriented approach," in *Proceedings 19th International Conference on Software Engineering (ICSE)*, Boston, 1997, pp. 380–389.
- [72] S. Pfleeger, "Maturity, models, and goals: how to build a metrics plan," *Journal of Systems and Software*, vol. 31, no. 2, pp. 143–55, Nov. 1995.
- [73] C. Tischer, A. Müller, M. Ketterer, and L. Geyer, "Why does it take that long? Establishing product lines in the automotive domain," in *Proceedings 11th International Software Product Line Conference (SPLC)*, Kyoto, Japan, 2007, pp. 269–274.
- [74] S. I. Hashmi and J. Baik, "Quantitative process improvement in XP using six sigma tools," in *Proceedings 7th International Conference on Computer and Information Science (ICIS)*, Portland, 2008, pp. 519–524.
- [75] E. Lee and M. Lee, "Development system security process of ISO/IEC TR 15504 and security considerations for software process improvement," in *Computational Science and its Applications*, ser. Lecture Notes in Computer Science. Berlin, Germany: Springer, 2005, vol. 3481, pp. 363–372.
- [76] D. Escala and M. Morisio, "A metric suite for a team PSP," in *Proceedings 5th International Software Metrics Symposium (METRICS)*, Bethesda, 1998, pp. 89–92.
- [77] A. Roan and P. Hebrard, "A PIE one year after: APPLY," in *International Conference on Product Focused Software Process Improvement (VTT Symposium)*, Oulu, Finland, 1999, pp. 606–19.
- [78] A. Borjesson, "Improve by improving software process improvers," *International Journal of Business Information Systems*, vol. 1, no. 3, pp. 310–38, Jan. 2006.
- [79] J. Haugh, "Never make the same mistake twice—using configuration control and error analysis to improve software quality," in *Proceedings 10th Digital Avionics Systems Conference*, Los Angeles, 1991, pp. 220–5.
- [80] C. Ebert, C. H. Parro, R. Suttels, and H. Kolarczyk, "Improving validation activities in a global software development," in *Proceedings 23rd International Conference on Software Engineering (ICSE)*, Toronto, Canada, 2001, pp. 545–554.
- [81] D. Damian and J. Chisan, "An empirical study of the complex relationships between requirements engineering processes and other processes that lead to payoffs in productivity, quality, and risk management," *IEEE Trans. Softw. Eng.*, vol. 32, no. 7, pp. 433–453, Jul. 2006.
- [82] D. Damian, J. Chisan, L. Vaidyanathasamy, and Y. Pal, "Requirements engineering and downstream software development: Findings from a case study," *Empirical Software Engineering*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 255–283, Jul. 2005.
- [83] C. Ebert, "The impacts of software product management," *Journal of Systems and Software*, vol. 80, no. 6, pp. 850–861, Jun. 2007.
- [84] M. T. Baldassarre, A. Bianchi, D. Caivano, and G. Visaggio, "An industrial case study on reuse oriented development," in *Proceedings 21st International Conference on Software Maintenance (ICSM)*, Budapest, Hungary, 2005, pp. 283–92.
- [85] O. Salo and P. Abrahamsson, "An iterative improvement process for agile software development," *Software Process Improvement and Practice*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 81–100, Jan. 2007.
- [86] S. Morad and T. Kuflik, "Conventional and open source software reuse at Orbotech - an industrial experience," in *Proceedings International Conference on Software - Science, Technology and Engineering (SWSTE)*, Herzlia, Israel, 2005, pp. 110–17.
- [87] A. Ahmed, M. Fraz, and F. Zahid, "Some results of experimentation with extreme programming paradigm," in *Proceedings 7th International Multi-Topic Conference (INMIC)*, Lahore, Pakistan, 2004, pp. 387–90.
- [88] L. Gou, Q. Wang, J. Yuan, Y. Yang, M. Li, and N. Jiang, "Quantitatively managing defects for iterative projects: An industrial experience report in China," in *Making Globally Distributed Software Development a Success Story*, ser. Lecture Notes in Computer Science. Berlin, Germany: Springer, 2008, vol. 5007, pp. 369–380.
- [89] M. Höst and C. Johansson, "Evaluation of code review methods through interviews and experimentation," *Journal of Systems & Software*, vol. 52, no. 2-3, pp. 113–20, Jun. 2000.
- [90] B. Shen and D. Ju, "On the measurement of agility in software process," in *Software Process Dynamics and Agility*, ser. Lecture Notes in Computer Science. Berlin, Germany: Springer, 2007, vol. 4470, pp. 25–36.

- [91] D. Winkler, B. Thurnher, and S. Biffl, "Early software product improvement with sequential inspection sessions: an empirical investigation of inspector capability and learning effects," in *Proceedings 33rd Euromicro Conference on Software Engineering and Advanced Applications (EUROMICRO)*, Lübeck, Germany, 2007, pp. 245–54.
- [92] K. Nelson and M. Ghods, "Evaluating the contributions of a structured software development and maintenance methodology," *Information Technology & Management*, vol. 3, no. 1-2, pp. 11–23, Jan. 2002.
- [93] T. Nishiyama, K. Ikeda, and T. Niwa, "Technology transfer macro-process. a practical guide for the effective introduction of technology," in *Proceedings 22nd International Conference on Software Engineering (ICSE)*, Limerick, Ireland, 2000, pp. 577–86.
- [94] C. Ebert, "Understanding the product life cycle: four key requirements engineering techniques," *IEEE Softw.*, vol. 23, no. 3, pp. 19–25, May 2006.
- [95] M. van Genuchten, C. van Dijk, H. Scholten, and D. Vogel, "Using group support systems for software inspections," *IEEE Softw.*, vol. 18, no. 3, pp. 60–5, May 2001.
- [96] F. Downey and G. Coleman, "Using SPI to achieve delivery objectives in e-commerce software development," *Software Process Improvement and Practice*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 327–333, Jul. 2008.
- [97] H. Leung, "Improving defect removal effectiveness for software development," in *Proceedings 2nd Euromicro Conference on Software Maintenance and Reengineering (CSMR)*, Florence, Italy, 1998, pp. 157–64.
- [98] J. Ramil and M. Lehman, "Defining and applying metrics in the context of continuing software evolution," in *Proceedings 7th International Software Metrics Symposium (METRICS)*, London, UK, 2000, pp. 199–209.
- [99] V. French, "Applying software engineering and process improvement to legacy defence system maintenance: an experience report," in *Proceedings 11th International Conference on Software Maintenance (ICSM)*, Opio (Nice), France, 1995, pp. 337–43.
- [100] K. Kautz, "Making sense of measurement for small organizations," *IEEE Softw.*, vol. 16, no. 2, pp. 14–20, Mar. 1999.
- [101] L. He and J. Carver, "PBR vs. checklist: A replication in the n-fold inspection context," in *Proceedings 5th International Symposium on Empirical Software Engineering*, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, 2006, pp. 95–104.
- [102] L. Damm and L. Lundberg, "Results from introducing component-level test automation and Test-Driven development," *Journal of Systems and Software*, vol. 79, no. 7, pp. 1001–14, Jul. 2006.
- [103] S. Biffl and M. Halling, "Software product improvement with inspection. a large-scale experiment on the influence of inspection processes on defect detection in software requirements documents," in *Proceedings 26th Euromicro Conference*, Maastricht, The Netherlands, 2000, pp. 262–9.
- [104] A. Nolan, "Learning from success," *IEEE Softw.*, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 97–105, Jan. 1999.
- [105] M. Visconti and L. Guzman, "A measurement-based approach for implanting SQA and SCM practices," in *Proceedings 20th International Conference of the Chilean Computer Science Society (SCCC)*, Santiago, Chile, 2000, pp. 126–34.
- [106] J. Andrade, J. Ares, O. Dieste, R. Garcia, M. Lopez, S. Rodriguez, and L. Verde, "Creation of an automated management software requirements environment: A practical experience," in *Proceedings 10th International Workshop on Database and Expert Systems Applications (DEXA)*, Florence, Italy, 1999, pp. 328–35.
- [107] F. Titze, "Improvement of a configuration management system," in *Proceedings 22nd International Conference on Software Engineering (ICSE)*, Limerick, Ireland, 2000, pp. 618–25.
- [108] B. Anda, E. Angelvik, and K. Ribu, "Improving estimation practices by applying use case models," in *Product Focused Software Process Improvement*, ser. Lecture Notes in Computer Science. Berlin, Germany: Springer, 2002, vol. 2559, pp. 383–97.
- [109] C. Ebert and J. D. Man, "e-R&D - effectively managing process diversity," *Annals of Software Engineering*, vol. 14, no. 1-4, pp. 73–91, Dec. 2002.
- [110] J. Momoh and G. Ruhe, "Release planning process improvement - an industrial case study," *Software Process Improvement and Practice*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 295–307, May 2006.

- [111] G. Giraud and P. Tonella, “Designing and conducting an empirical study on test management automation,” *Empirical Software Engineering*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 59–81, Mar. 2003.
- [112] J. Hössler, O. Kath, M. Soden, M. Born, and S. Saito, “Significant productivity enhancement through model driven techniques: a success story,” in *Proceedings 10th International Enterprise Distributed Object Computing Conference (EDOC)*, Hong Kong, China, 2006, pp. 367–373.
- [113] T. Bruckhaus, N. H. Madhavii, I. Janssen, and J. Henshaw, “The impact of tools on software productivity,” *IEEE Softw.*, vol. 13, no. 5, pp. 29–38, Sep. 1996.